

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 12, No. 5; May 28, 2006

Dear Readers:

Here is the latest issue of J.UCS, with four very interesting papers. The first one deals with on-line monitoring of metric temporal logic, the second one with efficient multi-precision arithmetic extending of Karatsuba's algorithm, the third one is a break-through paper on algorithmical tilings $\{p,q\}$ of the hyperbolic plane, and the fourth one is a nice survey of completeness in the boolean hierarchy.

Hope you enjoy the papers! Please continue to contribute to J.UCS and spread the word, and you may as well spread an interesting rumor: as of January 2007 access to J.UCS will be free of charge, thanks to the support of a number of research and university organisations in Graz!

With best wishes for a good summer (or winter, whichever may apply!),

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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